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Research Article

**AN ASSESSMENT OF HESS TEST REACTIVITY AMONG DHF
PATIENTS: HESS TEST AS A DIAGNOSTIC TOOL****Dr. Arslan Arshad, Dr. Faiza Noor, Dr. Hafiza Fizza Zahid**
Jinnah Hospital, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: DHF is a complicated type of Dengue contamination. The excessive capillary permeability and thrombocytopenia with simultaneous haema concentration are the symptoms of this infection. Fever because of Dengue is a serious issue faced by people mainly by countries of South-East Asia. The patients diagnosed with DHF has been suggested to encounter Hess lest or Tourniquet test. The study aims to check the reactivity of the Hess test in the diagnosis of DHF.

Methods: Total people selected for this research study were 50. These people were the sufferers from DHF. The time duration of this study was from September to October 2017. This study was organized in Allied Hospital, Faisalabad when infection of Dengue burst out. Standard procedure was applied to these patients and the Hess test or tourniquet test was organized.

Results: Total 50 patients of DHF were included in the study. The Hess test was observing positive in 26 patients. These 50 patients were categorized into 4 different groups. This grouping was related to rash, bleeding, non-bleeding and rash. Rash was present in 9 patients. Out of these just 6 patients were observed with positive Hess test., 6 were observed with positive Hess test out of 11 patients. In the same way, 23 patients were found with non-bleeding non-rash and Hess test was positive in 08 patients. On the other hand, in the bleeding and rash group, 7 patients were observed and positive Hess test was observed in 06 patients.

Conclusion: Tourniquet test was also conducted on patients. Out of all DHF patients, 52% were noticed with a positive tourniquet test. The result indicated that the best indication for DHF is the Hess test. It is also concluded that to prohibit an indication of DHF in a fevered patient's negative tourniquet may be inadequate. For an indication of DHF, it is very important to remake the clinical standard.

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INTRODUCTION:

Infection caused by dengue is a serious issue faced by people mainly by the tropical and subtropical countries of South East Asia [1]. Single strands of RNA positive flavivirus transported by a mosquito is responsible for dengue infection. Flavivirus has four serotypes DEN [2]. It caused by the illness of degree from simple to severe. The fever caused by dengue may be simple unidentified fever or fever to that extent which endangers life. Dengue shock syndrome and dengue hemorrhagic fever are life taking illness [3]. In the present time, except Europe, all the continents are affected with dengue to more or less extent. In Asia, America and some Pacific island, the presence of epidemic dengue hemorrhagic fever are noticed [4]. On the annual basis, 80 million people become the victim of dengue, as the component of dengue is present in about two-third areas of the world. In 1990, over two-third of DHF cases were experienced by South East Asia mainly Nam AND Thailand. Comparatively to last five years during 1991 – 1995 more people were subjected to Dengue in the Sri Lankan, Singapore, Cambodia, Myanmar, India, Malaysia, Philippines and Lao people's Democratic Republic [5]. So, it is noticed that in the Asian countries the prevalence of Dengue is greater as compared to other countries.

Aga Khan University Hospital in Pakistan first observed the outburst of Dengue [6]. This was because of serotype DV. This research was reported in 1994. Another outbreak was observed in the province of Baluchistan by Paul *et al* in 1998. Co-circulation of DV and DV2 was responsible for this outbreak [7]. In three main hospital of Karachi, similar research was conducted during September to December 2005. In this study, the presence of DV3 is reported due to genotyping of Sample selection [8]. In 2006 and 2011, the biggest and serious burst of dengue was encountered by Pakistan. Important serotype reported were DV2 and DV3 [9]. Plasma leakage is the authentic mark that differentiates DF from DHF. When the vascular permeability is enhanced leakage of plasma results [10]. Involvement

of liver, rash, plasma leakage, thrombocytopenia, bleeding tendency and fever are some other clinical aspects of DHF.

When this illness reaches on serious condition, standard tourniquet test is conducted. Capillary weakness, as well as thrombocytopenia, are observed by this test. For 5-minute blood pressure knock is elevated at 80mm Hg in this test. Tourniquet test is considered positive if the 1-inch square area at cubital fossa, over 10 petechiae are observed. It was employed for DHF and DSS detection according to the recommendation of WHO in 1997. But it was not able to diagnosis DF [11]. IN 2009, WHO considered it eligible for the diagnosis of DF, DHF and DSS [12]. Tourniquet test is useful for identification of dengue in children who were admitted in hospitals and are with high specificity (94%) and less sensitivity (42%) [13]. This is proved during the deflection of dengue infection among Vietnamese children. A similar study was also organized in Malaysia. The sensitivity of the tourniquet test was 83% and specificity was 23.5% in Malaysian children [14].

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Total people selected for this research study were 50. These people were the sufferers from DHF. The time duration of this study was from September to October 2017. This study was organized in Allied Hospital, Faisalabad when infection of Dengue burst out. The patients were suffering from bleeding, rashes, high fever and a low number of platelets. Hess test or tourniquet test was conducted. For 5 minutes' blood pressure knock is elevated at 80 mm Hg in this test. The test was considered positive if at 1-inch square area at cubital fossa, above 10 petechiae are observed. Bleeding, fever, haemoconcentration. 20% from the baseline, BP plasma leakage and pulse were measured initially for the identification of dengue hemorrhagic fever.

RESULTS:

The outcomes are as under:

Table: Research Outcomes Stratification (Gender Wise)

Outcomes		Males	Females	Total
Hess Test	Positive	14	12	26
	Negative	8	16	24
	Total	22	28	50
Rash Only	Positive	4	2	6
	Negative	1	2	3
	Total	5	4	9

Bleeding Only	Positive	2	4	6
	Negative	1	4	5
	Total	3	8	11
Bleeding Rash	Positive	4	2	6
	Negative	0	1	1
	Total	4	3	7
Non-Bleeding and Non-Rash	Positive	5	3	8
	Negative	8	7	15
	Total	13	10	23

DISCUSSION:

The study concluded that standard tourniquet test is important for the detection of dengue infection.

The study indicated that positive tourniquet test was positive in 43.47% patients and negative tourniquet test was a presence in 56.53% patients.

CONCLUSION:

Tourniquet test was also conducted on patients. Out of all DHF patients, 52% were noticed with a positive tourniquet test. The result indicated that the best indication for DHF is Hess test. It is also concluded that to prohibit an indication of DHF in a febrile patient's negative tourniquet may be inadequate. For an indication of DHF, it is very important to remake the clinical standard.

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